

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF THE OPEN-HOLE COMPOSITES LAMINATES USING SFEM METHOD AND TEST VALIDATION

Xiuhua Chen¹, Yin Yu¹, Hai Wang¹ and Jian Zhao¹

¹ School of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Shanghai Jiao Tong University,
800 Dongchuan Road, Shanghai, 200240, China

Email: chenxiuhua@sjtu.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.sjtu.edu.cn>

Keywords: Digital image correlation (DIC), open-hole composite laminate, progressive failure analysis, s-version finite element method (SFEM)

ABSTRACT

In this paper, application of the s-version finite element method (SFEM) in the progressive failure analysis of open-hole composite plates is investigated. First, the tension tests of the composite laminates with a central hole are performed. The mechanical behavior and failure mechanisms of the open-hole composite laminates are investigated. A digital image correlation (DIC) system is introduced for capturing the strain field of the surface layer. Second, a new modeling methodology for the open-hole composite laminates based on the SFEM method is presented. Patran command language (PCL) is employed for fast modeling and visualization. FORTRAN language and PARDISO package are incorporated in the procedure for high computational efficiency. Proper failure criteria and material degradation rule in the progressive failure analysis (PFA) are calibrated by comparison of different combinations. Good agreement is obtained in the strength prediction and the strain field during the failure process, compared with the experimental and DIC results. The PFA based on the SFEM model of the open-hole composites is validated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been widely used in recent years due to their high stiffness to weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and other advantages [1]. Notches are inevitable in composite structures to meet the design and manufacture requirements, such as holes and cutouts in the laminates drilled to attach the bolts or rivets to the main structures. The introduction of holes can substantially increase the stress concentration and significantly reduce the strength of composite, thereby creating potential failure regions. Therefore, the evaluation of residual strength and the progressive failure mechanism have become the main concern for many researchers and engineers.

The open-hole test methods of composite laminates have been adopted as the industrial standards to obtain the notched strength [2,3]. Besides, it is the direct way to perform the open-hole tests so as to observe the failure damage process [4,5,6]. Embedded FBG sensors [7], non-destructive testing of X-ray and C-scan [8,9] were employed in the open-hole test to determine the detailed progressive damage process. Recently, the advanced digital image correlation (DIC) system was also introduced to capture the strain field [10]. Flatscher [11] conducted this photogrammetry system to investigate the non-linear behavior, including intra-ply plasticity, damage and softening in the open-hole composite plates. Ercin [12] used this technique to identify the first-ply failure load of the outer ply.

It should be stressed that the trends obtained from the strength data in expensive and time-consuming experiments were quite limited since the experimental data were largely dependent on the material properties, stacking sequence, and geometry of specimens [13]. Hence, computational methods have attracted extensive attention, which can be categorized into: (1) analytical method; and (2) finite element method (FEM).

As a typical analytical method, the characteristic distance approach and modifications are widely used in the prediction of the residual strength in the 2D open-hole composite laminate. The criteria in this approach include the point stress criterion (PSC) and the average stress criterion (ASC) introduced by Whitney and Nuismer [14]. However, in spite of their simplicity and accuracy, the precision of this semi-empirical method is largely based on the accurate test data of the unnotched laminate, which are required for the definition of the characteristic distance [4]. Recently, other new analytical methods have been proposed by some researchers. Camanho [15] developed a fast and accurate strength prediction method for open-hole composite laminates subjected to tension. Also, in the cohesive zone model [16], the open-hole compressive (OHC) strength of any multi-directional composite laminate can be estimated analytically from material constituent properties. Taking this advantage, Soutis [17] successfully applied the model to study the effect of ply blocking in open-hole composite laminates.

In comparison with the analytical method, the finite element method can better describe the stress distribution around the open hole and the progressive failure process [18]. In the literatures, [4] the shell element was used incorporating the basic ply failure criteria and material property degradation, which showed good agreement between prediction and measured strength results. Suemasu [5] used three-dimensional brick elements to obtain the stress distribution around the open hole in the composite laminates subjected to compression. Jiang et al. [8] introduced a simple damage state variable in the constitutive formulation for cohesive interfaces to simulate the delamination and splitting process of composites. Van [19] proposed the phantom-node method for representing matrix cracks to model complex failure mechanisms in composite laminates, coupled with interface elements for delamination and a continuum damage model for fiber failure.

Apparently, in the open-hole problem, the fine element size in the vicinity of the hole is essential in order to capture the high stress gradients, whereas increasingly coarse elements in the transition region away from the hole are helpful in the above-mentioned traditional finite element models. This common meshing technique obviously raises the modeling difficulty and reduces the computational efficiency. Recently, Belytschko [20] developed the extended finite element method (XFEM), a variation of the conventional FEM, to model arbitrary discontinuities. When meshing the plate with a circular hole under uniaxial tension using the XFEM method [21], evenly distributed triangular elements were adopted in the whole region without a hole. The hole was represented by the level set function in the XFEM implementation, rather than being explicitly modeled in classical FEM. Without the transition elements in the XFEM model, good agreement was also achieved between XFEM method and classical FEM.

Fish [22] first proposed another alternative finite element methodology for modeling notches called the s-version finite element method (SFEM). In the SFEM method, there are two independently modeled regions: a global region, representing the general loading with coarse meshes, and a local region of interest (i.e. cracks, holes, and delamination) with finer meshes superimposed on the global region. Owing to this special modeling technique, the elements in the traditional FEM are no longer necessary to smoothly transit from coarse elements away from the stress concentration area. With convenient modeling characteristics, SFEM has been applied to various fields, such as stress concentration analysis [23] and propagation of metal crack [24] ship structures [25], elastodynamic problems [26], simulation of adhesive joints [27], structural topology optimization [28]. However, this novel finite element method is rarely reported in the open-hole problem.

Some researchers have also extended this s-version finite element method to solve problems in composite materials. Fish [29] introduced it to analyze composite laminates and capture the localized phenomena around the free edge, where a two-dimensional equivalent single layer (ESL) model for the global domain was imposed by a local mesh with 3D elements [30]. Heterogeneity in global and local regions was first taken into account by Takano [31]. In the literature [32], implementation techniques and effectiveness of SFEM were discussed through the buckling analysis of delaminated composite plates under compression. In the work of Kurashiki and his co-workers [33], SFEM was successfully used for the evaluation of mechanical properties of non-crimp fabric (NCF) composites and braided composites. Combined with XFEM, this method was developed to accurately evaluate the interlaminar stresses in thick composite laminates [34]. Sellitto [35] used SFEM to estimate the delamination initiation impact and the size of the impact resulting from delaminations in composite

thin plates subjected to low velocity impact. So far, application of SFEM in progressive failure analysis of open-hole composite laminates has not yet been reported.

In this paper, a new modeling methodology using SFEM for the progressive analysis in composite laminates with a circular hole is proposed. Firstly, the tension strength of CYCOM977-2 laminates is measured using ASTM D5766 standard test method. In the test, the full-field measurement method is simultaneously used. Then, the modeling methodology for the open-hole composite plates based on SFEM is described in detail. The Patran command language (PCL) used for parametric modeling and failure visualization, FORTRAN language and direct sparse solver (PARDISO) are adopted in the procedure. The accuracy and effectiveness of this methodology are demonstrated by comparison of the strength prediction and failure process with the experimental results and DIC results.

2 OPEN-HOLE TEST

The open-hole specimens used were made of CYCOM977-2/IMS-194 material, a unidirectional carbon/epoxy pre-preg, with a nominal ply thickness of 0.188mm. The material properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 CYCOM977-2/IMS-194 material properties

E1(GPa)	E2(GPa)	G12(GPa)	XT(MPa)	XC(MPa)	YT(MPa)	YC(MPa)	S12(MPa)	ν_{12}
149.2	8.9	4	2926	1648	80	284	138	0.341

The open-hole specimen subjected to quasi-static tension loading is schematically presented in Figure 1. The length (l), width (w), and diameter of the central through-thickness hole (d) are 300mm, 36mm, and 6mm respectively. The grip length at either end of the specimen is 45mm. The composite laminate with the stacking sequence of $[45/-45/0/0/45/-45/90]_s$ was adopted, with 0_0 being the direction of the applied tensile loading. Five strain gauges were attached to the specimens, the positions of which are schematically shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2b.

Figure 1. Geometry of the composite specimen

The holes were carefully drilled using sacrificial plates on both surfaces of the specimens in the preparation stage. The test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D5766 at room temperature by using MTS® testing system and the non-contact measuring system Aramis® Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system as shown in Figure 2. The DIC system was used in this work to obtain the full-field displacement on the outer 45° ply. The specimen was loaded at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min and was applied monotonically until specimen failure happened.

Six specimens test are carried out. The failure modes of these specimens are fiber break combined with delamination between adjacent layers. The damage images are taken by optical scanning and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in detail, which are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively. The load vs. displacement curve of the six specimens is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 2. Test of the open-hole laminate under tension load

Figure 3. Optical scanning picture of the open-hole laminate test specimens

Figure 4. SEM Photo of the fiber break and delamination on open-hole area

Figure 5. Load vs. displacement curves of the open-hole tension test

From Figure 5, the stiffness open-hole specimens are degrading when the load reached about 40 KN. The ultimate loads and the tension strengths are presented in table 2.

Table 2 Results of the open-hole composite tension tests

Number	Ultimate load (KN)	Tension strength (MPa)
OHT-1-1	56.6	604.8
OHT-1-2	58.3	622.5
OHT-1-3	57.1	610.0
OHT-1-4	58.2	621.4
OHT-1-5	58.3	623.1
OHT-1-6	58.1	620.9
Average	57.8	617.1

3 PROGRESSIVE ANALYSES OF OPEN-HOLE COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING SFEM

3.1 SFEM OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH AN OPEN HOLE

In the open-hole problem, the structure is discretized by the global finite element mesh as a whole, and the vicinity of the hole is discretized by the local mesh when using the SFEM method. As illustrated in Figure 6, the finer local mesh is superimposed on the global mesh. Global and local regions are denoted as Ω^G and Ω^L , respectively. Meshes on both regions are generated independently of each other, in which the hole is only described in the local mesh.

Figure 6. Illustration for an open-hole problem solved by SFEM

Figure 7. Mapping between two coordinates

Displacement fields in the global and local meshes are represented by $u_i^G(x)$ and $u_i^L(x)$, respectively. x is the position vector of a material point. In the global mesh, the displacements are expressed by $u_i^G(x)$. While in the overlay region, displacements are given by the combination of those based on the global and local meshes. So, the displacements are expressed by:

$$u_i = \begin{cases} u_i^G(x) & x \in \Omega^G - \Omega^L \\ u_i^G(x) + u_i^L(x) & x \in \Omega^L \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The boundaries in the global and local mesh are denoted as Γ^G and Γ^L , respectively. In order to satisfy the C^0 continuity condition, the displacements on the coupling boundary Γ^{GL} are constrained by:

$$u(x) = u^G(x), \quad u^L(x) = 0, \quad x \in \Gamma^{GL} \quad (2)$$

According to the virtual work principle, the governing equation is obtained.

$$\int_{\Omega^G} \delta u_{i,j} D_{ijkl} u_{k,l} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega^G} \delta u_i b_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma^t} \delta u_i t_i d\Gamma^t \quad (3)$$

Substituting Equation (1) into Equation (3) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega^G - \Omega^L} \delta u_{i,j}^G D_{ijkl}^G u_{k,l}^G d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^L} (\delta u_{i,j}^G + \delta u_{i,j}^L) D_{ijkl}^L (u_{k,l}^G + u_{k,l}^L) d\Omega \\ & = \int_{\Omega^G - \Omega^L} \delta u_i^G b_i d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^L} (\delta u_i^G + \delta u_i^L) b_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma^t} \delta u_i^G t_i d\Gamma^t \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where D_{ijkl}^G is the fourth order tensor representing the Hooke's law in the global region, and D_{ijkl}^L is the Hook tensor in the local region. Here, the material properties in both regions are represented differently considering the heterogeneity between the global and local region [31]. As the specimen is continuously loaded, failure occurs first in the local region around the hole. Thus, the differences of the material properties in different regions can be carefully taken into account after failure occurs.

After discretization in the global and local domains, the formulation of SFEM in a matrix form is derived:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K^G] & [K^{GL}] \\ [K^{GL}]^T & [K^L] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{u^G\} \\ \{u^L\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{f^G\} \\ \{f^L\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $[K^G]$ and $[K^L]$ are respectively stiffness matrices of the global mesh and the local mesh, submatrices $[K^{GL}]$ represents the coupling stiffness matrix involving the interaction between two independent meshes, $\{f^G\}$ and $\{f^L\}$ are the traction vectors of the global and local meshes, respectively. Submatrices $[K^G]$, $[K^L]$, $[K^{GL}]$ and $[K^{LG}]$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} [K^G] = & \int_{\Omega^G} [B^G]^T [D^G] [B^G] d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^L] [B^G] d\Omega \\ & - \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^G] [B^G] d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$[K^L] = \int_{\Omega^L} [B^L]^T [D^L] [B^L] d\Omega \quad (7)$$

$$[K^{GL}] = [K^{LG}]^T = \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^L] [B^L] d\Omega \quad (8)$$

where, $[D^G]$ and $[D^L]$ are respectively the elastic matrices of the global and local meshes, and $[B^G]$ and $[B^L]$ are the strain-displacement matrices of the global and local meshes, respectively.

It is inefficient to adopt traditional linear sparse matrix equation solvers in terms of the memory usage and total CPU time, owing to the strong coupling between the global and local meshes in the sparse symmetric stiffness matrix. Hence, the popular package PARDISO is adopted in the SFEM method. This effective and robust package is readily performed for solving large sparse symmetric on shared memory multiprocessors.

The assembly of the stiffness matrices [KGG] and [KLL] can be easily accomplished in the conventional way. However, special attention should be paid to the calculation of the coupling matrix [KGL]. By discretization, the element stiffness matrix of [KGL] can be expressed as

$$[K^{GL}]_e = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n [B_i(\xi^G, \eta^G)]^T [D^L] [B_j(\xi^L, \eta^L)] t |J| W_r W_s \quad (9)$$

where subscript e denotes the element stiffness matrix, m and n are the number of quadrature points along the ξ and η direction in the isoparametric coordinate system, respectively, W_r and W_s are the Gauss integration coefficients, and $|J|$ is the determinant of the Jacobian matrix. The material properties are stored in each quadrature point. The value of local elastic matrix [DL] can vary as failure may occur at any integration point during the loading. The integration coordinate (ξ^G, η^G) in the global element is the mapping from integration coordinate (ξ^L, η^L) in the local element, as outlined in Figure 7.

Traditionally, an iterative process is required to obtain the global integration coordinate. The calculation of the coupling matrix [KGL] can be rather inefficient and time-consuming, when the shapes of the global elements are irregularly generated and the number of the local elements is increasingly larger. Thus, in order to improve the computational efficiency, the fast ‘‘fixed grid modeling’’ strategy where only regular rectangular elements are modeled in the global region is employed in this paper.

In the finite element analysis of the composite plates, a three-dimensional model is desirable to obtain accurate stresses and strains along the through-thickness direction. However, due to the long computational time in a three-dimensional analysis, two-dimensional analysis using plate or shell finite elements is commonly conducted.

Specifically, in this open-hole test, the in-plane uniaxial loading is applied to the specimens. So, the three-dimensional analysis is not computationally essential here. Furthermore, since the focus of this paper is mainly on studying the applicability of the SFEM method to open-hole composite plates, a two-dimensional analysis introduced in the present simulation is computationally sufficient and economic enough. This two-dimensional analysis is based on first-order shear deformation plate theory (FSDT) and classical laminate plate theory (CLPT). For simplicity, a 4-node shell element with six degrees of freedom at each node is used.

3.2 IMPLEMENTATION OF PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS

In the progressive failure analysis, the failure mode should be accurately detected and the material degradation method should be properly opted. Many researchers have been proposed a number of failure criteria in order to predict the failure load, such as maximum stress, Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu, Hashin. However, there are no standard failure criteria proved to be versatile in any stress states. The selection of degradation method is also varied. Degradation rules presented by Chang, Tan and Camanho are commonly used in the failure analysis. In the present study, appropriate failure criteria and degradation rule are determined by comparing the experimental result with each result obtained by different combination of the above mentioned methods.

Stresses at each material point (Gauss point) of each ply are checked based on the chosen criteria, after the convergence of the nonlinear analysis arrives at each load increment. So once any failure mode is satisfied, the material properties are degraded according to the degradation model and thus the dropped load-carrying capacity can be simulated. As noted in Figure 8, if any degradation is performed, then a re-establishing equilibrium will be made. The external load is incremented continuously until the calculated reaction force plunges suddenly, which indicates the occurrence of failure.

In the pre and post processing part, the Patran command language (PCL) is introduced for model generation and visualization because of its high performance.

Since the model in the open-hole problem is symmetric and simple, the geometry and meshing operation are automatically carried out by the parametric programming. "Group" tool in MSC.Patran is utilized to build the "global model", "local model", and "coupling boundary". After meshing, the information about the elements, coordinates and groups is written into text files, which will be further read by the main procedure.

The displacements at each node and failure status at each integration point can be calculated by SFEM method. Moreover, plot contours of the strain field and failure mode could be visually generated by adopting the database functions in PCL.

Using PCL, FORTRAN, and PARDISO, the modeling methodology for the progressive analysis of open-hole composite plates based on SFEM is proposed. The calculation is primarily computed in the FORTRAN environment. Geometric construction and mesh generation of the open-hole model are readily achieved by parametric modeling using customized PCL subroutines. The high-performance package, PARDISO, is well incorporated within FORTRAN. Then the failure will be checked at each iteration. Afterwards, visualizing the failure pattern is accomplished by calling external PCL files. Text files are available for transferring the information of models and results between FORTRAN and PCL.

The SFEM program for failure analysis of the open-hole composite plate is developed in Microsoft visual studio 2008, which is run on a PC with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i5 CPU at 2.67 GHz and a 2 GB of RAM under the Microsoft Windows XP operating system.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND VERIFICATION

As shown in Figure 8, one rectangular element represents the global region, and the square local region around the hole is meshed by uniformly refined elements. First, the eighth part of the local mesh colored in grey is built by parametric programming, and then the whole region is formed by the symmetry utility in MSC.Patran. The diameter of the inner circle is the same as that of the hole. The

square side length of the local region is set to be the width of the specimen, which could cover the critical region where the crack may propagate along the $\pm 45^\circ$ directions as recommended in literature.²⁵ Nodes on one end are constrained in both directions, while tensile load in the form of enforced displacement (ED) is applied incrementally on the other end.

Figure 8. SFEM model for open-hole composite plates

In the test, when the displacement reached around 3.4mm, the applied load dropped abruptly at approximately 57.8 KN. The final failure occurred nearly instantly in all specimens, with no warnings on the onset of failure other than some “ping” sound heard.

In order to choose a suitable failure scheme, different combinations of the failure criteria and the degradation rule are examined. The examined failure criteria involve the maximum stress, Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu and Hashin criteria, while the degradation rules for test are the Chang, Tan and Camanho. As summarized in Table 3. Large discrepancy is discovered when the maximum stress criteria is adopted (in the cases 1-3). Also, it is interesting to note that a good correlation is obtained in the case 8, where the Hashin criteria and Camanho degradation rule are employed. The strain field produced by this better failure scheme will be further compared with the DIC result.

Table 3. Errors of the simulation results using different combination of failure criteria and degradation rule

Case	Failure criteria	Degradation rule	Ultimate displacement		Ultimate load	
			Predicted (mm)	Error (%)	Predicted (KN)	Error (%)
1	Maximum stress	Chang	3.9	15.17	71.66	24.88
2	Maximum stress	Tan	4.1	21.08	70.34	22.58
3	Maximum stress	Camanho	4.1	21.08	74.92	30.56
4	Tsai-Hill	Tan	3.1	-8.45	57.62	0.42
5	Tsai-Wu	Tan	3.7	9.27	62.95	9.71
6	Hashin	Chang	4.1	21.08	73.77	28.56
7	Hashin	Tan	3.6	6.32	61.76	7.63
8	Hashin	Camanho	3.3	-2.54	60.43	5.31

As listed in Table 4, the strain values located in five strain gauges are compared with those calculated by the proposed method. The evaluated point is set to be the center of the corresponding strain gauges. The average error of strain values in the critical and far-field positions using the SFEM method is approximately 6.32%. Therefore, good agreement in the strain field is obtained between the experiment and the SFEM method and the effectiveness of this method in calculation of strain values is well verified.

In this test, the DIC system is also introduced to identify the failure mechanism on the surface ply. The strain field distribution comparison of both x and y direction between DIC and SFEM results are shown in Figure 9. The region for comparison is a rectangular shape located around the open hole with a side length equal to the specimen width. The strain value shown in the color bar of the DIC images is carefully calibrated based on the strain values measured by the fifth strain gauge. In Figure 11, the

strain trends illustrated in both plot contours are similar, and the strain values in both methods are approximately of the same magnitude.

Table 4. Comparison of strain values between simulation results using the SFEM method and the experiment in specific positions

ED	Strain gauge No.	Experiment	SFEM	Error (%)
1.0 mm	①	0.00346	0.00294	-15.07
	②	-0.00383	-0.00362	-5.56
	③	0.00667	0.00522	-21.83
	④	-0.00154	-0.00119	-22.64
	⑤	0.00528	0.00476	-9.89
1.5 mm	①	0.00473	0.00409	-13.42
	②	-0.00541	-0.00417	-22.95
	③	0.00938	0.00809	-13.72
	④	-0.00223	-0.00258	15.73
	⑤	0.00718	0.00714	-0.57
2.0 mm	①	0.00603	0.00472	-21.71
	②	-0.00743	-0.00797	7.26
	③	0.01194	0.01437	20.40
	④	-0.00785	-0.00633	-19.29
	⑤	0.00891	0.00952	6.85
2.5 mm	①	0.00711	0.00562	-20.95
	②	-0.01239	-0.01287	3.85
	③	0.01434	0.01712	19.45
	④	-0.00998	-0.00752	-24.63
	⑤	0.01061	0.01190	12.21

Figure 9. Comparison of strain field between DIC and SFEM results

The strain comparison in both the specific points and plot contours shows that the SFEM method is comparable with the conventional measurement, either by using strain gauges or the digital image correlation technique.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The s-version finite element method (SFEM) is first applied in the failure analysis of open-hole composite plates. The ability of the SFEM method to predict the residual strength of open-hole laminate composites subjected to tensile loading is demonstrated.

First, the open-hole tension test is conducted. The mechanical properties and the failure mode are observed. The ultimate load and the tension strength are obtained. Then, the progressive analysis methodology is formulated for open-hole composite laminates based on SFEM. The progressive analysis method involves the SFEM method, finite element analysis, proper failure criteria and material degradation rule. Afterwards, the implementation procedure of the proposed method is stated. High computational efficiency of the procedure is readily achieved by employing PCL for modeling and visualization, FORTRAN for programming and PARDISO for solving highly complicated equations. The flow chart of the simulation is also given.

The example of the open-hole composite plates well proves that the proposed methodology based on SFEM significantly reduces modeling difficulty and computational memory usage. By comparison with the experiment and DIC results, good agreement is shown in the measurement of strain and the prediction of damage process.

In future applications, this novel modeling technique could be extended to the failure analyses of more types of lay-ups and other complicated notched composite structures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to Mr. Zhen Li for the computer program code.

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